

MEANS OF FORMATION OF THE CONTENT AND METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE QUALITIES OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH.

Terdu preschool education methodology
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Annotation: In this article, improving the pedagogical skills of the educator and developing the creative qualities of the educator will help to create new ideas different from the traditional approach to the organization of educational processes, not to think in one mold, originality, initiative, not tolerating ambiguity. Consequently, they talked about organizing the professional activity of a pedagogue-educator with creative qualities.

Key words: creative qualities of educators, education, natural and social, creative ability of pedagogues-educators, pedagogical problems

Аннотация: В данной статье совершенствование педагогического мастерства педагога и развитие творческих качеств педагога поможет создать новые идеи, отличные от традиционного подхода к организации учебного процесса, не мыслить единым шаблоном, оригинальностью, инициативностью, не терпит двусмысленности. Следовательно, речь шла об организации профессиональной деятельности педагога-воспитателя, обладающего творческими качествами.

Ключевые слова: творческие качества педагогов, образование природное и социальное, творческие способности педагогов-воспитателей, педагогические проблемы.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarbiyachi pedagogning kretivlik sifatlarini rivojlantirish pedagogik qobilyatlarini takomillashtirish ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonlarini tashkil etishga an'anaviy yondashishdan farqli yangi g'oyalarni yaratish, bir qolipda

fikrlamaslik, o'ziga xoslik, tashabbuskorlik, noaniqlikka toqat qilmaslikka yordam beradi. Binobarin, kreativlik sifatlariga ega pedagog-tarbiyachi kasbiy faoliyatini tashkil etish xaqida so'z yuritligan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarbiyachining kreativlik sifatleri, ta'lim-tarbiya, tabiiy va ijtimoiy, pedagog-tarbiyachilarning kreativlik qobiliyati, pedagogik muammolar.

Introduction. Creativity (lat., eng. "to create", "creativity" - an independent factor describing the readiness of a person to develop new ideas, expresses the meaning of creative ability, which is a part of talent. Creativity of a person is in his thinking, communication, It is manifested in emotions, in certain types of activities. Creativity characterizes the individual as a whole, his mental acuity. Creativity is also manifested as an important factor of talent Creativity, according to Torrens, is the expression of sensitivity to the contradiction of knowledge and practical actions, based on the examination and modification of hypotheses creativity is formed and developed at certain stages. Having creative qualities of a teacher directs his personal ability, natural and social power to quality and effective organization of his work. Possessing the creative qualities of a pedagogue helps them to create new ideas different from the traditional approach in organizing educational processes, not to think in a single mold, originality, initiative, not tolerating uncertainty. Therefore, a pedagogue-pedagogue with creative qualities should be creative in organizing his professional activities, be active in creating new, advanced ideas that serve to develop children's educational activities and personal qualities, advanced pedagogy it is necessary to independently assimilate achievements and experiences. "learning" focuses on having the experience of continuous, coherent feedback about pedagogical achievements with colleagues. Usually, pedagogues-pedagogues' creativity consists in the desire to solve pedagogical problems, to carry out scientific research or scientific projects. is provided, formed and gradually improved and developed through improvement and mutual creative cooperation. As in the case of any specialist, the foundation for the creativity of future pedagogues is laid in the

student years and it develops consistently in the organization of professional activity. It is important for the future pedagogue to direct himself to creative activity and to be able to organize this activity effectively. In the organization of creative activities, the teacher should pay special attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, as well as creating creative products of a pedagogical nature. The teacher's creative approach to solving problems and situations helps to form his emotional and volitional qualities. The pedagogue puts problematic issues in front of him and faces evidence that contradicts his existing knowledge and life experience. As a result, he feels the need to work on himself, to study independently. A teacher's research, scientific or creative projects will further develop his creative potential. A teacher cannot create by himself. His creative ability is formed through consistent study and work on himself over a period of time.

Feedback

Side panels

History

Saved

Contributions

Modern education requires creativity from pedagogues and pedagogues working in all types of educational institutions. The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is usually considered a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, sense of humor and freedom. In the East, on the contrary, they understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness. Although Western and Eastern peoples have different views on creativity, representatives of both cultures highly value this quality and its possession. A teacher's creativity is shaped by his innovative approaches. A teacher's creativity includes initiative, effective communication, high political and social status, foresight, quick response to the situation they need to perceive. A pedagogue who lacks self-confidence changes his attitude as the

situation changes. A person who does not believe in himself and others cannot inspire confidence. The essence of creativity is that intelligence is the mental potential of a person, and creativity is the ability to freely use this mental potential directed towards the goal. Creative qualities of a teacher-pedagogue. A pedagogue-pedagogue does not become creative by himself. His creativity is formed by consistent study and work on himself over a period of time, and it gradually improves and develops. As with any specialist, the foundation for future pedagogues to be creative is laid in the student years, and it is the organization of professional activity.

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